

IMPACT OF SCHOOL ADMINISTRATION STRUCTURE ON SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN ENUGU EDUCATION ZONE IN ENUGU STATE.

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ABSTRACT: The central thesis of this study is on the evaluation of the impact of school administration structure on secondary school student's academic performance in Enugu Education zone in Enugu State. To carry out this evaluation, 122 school teachers and secondary school principals in three Local governments in Enugu Education zone were used for the study, comprising of 26 teachers and 76 secondary school principals. The 122 questionnaires distributed to the respondents were dully completed and returned and were subsequently used in the analysis. Equally, personal interviews and visits were made to the schools used for the study, in addition to the distribution of the questionnaires. The data were analyzed by the use of tables and frequencies, while the formulated hypotheses were tested by the use of Z-test statistical technique. At the end of the study, it was revealed that good hierarchy of authority, proper delegation of authority to subordinates in form of division of labour, having adequate personnel that are seasoned in terms of qualification, skills and knowledge. And expertise impacts positively on the performance of students both in internal and external examinations. The study equally revealed that there are appropriate ways by which an organizational structure can incorporate employee inputs. These includes: employee trainings, mentoring, positive cultures, credible communication build up, appreciation via compensation and benefits etc. These aforementioned, when incorporated will give the employees sense of belonging. In view of the findings of the study, the study recommended among others that, to ensure a workable and functional organizational structure, there should be free flow of information, necessary to promote co-ordination and effectiveness of employees in the institution. Again, there is need to design organizational structure around the institutional goals, and there should be employee's roles allocations and relation because they are key factors that have significant positive effect on the institutional effectiveness.

Keywords: School Academic Structure, Secondary School Students and Academic Performance.

Introduction

A school is an educational institution dedicated to teaching and learning. An establishment offering specialized instructions, this specialized instruction ensures that students acquire certain skills and experience which tends to bring about anew change

in behavior of a student, which is the chief goal of any educational institution. (NTI, 2015) A school is also a place where teaching and learning takes place under the guidance of a teacher or an instructor. For a school to achieve its aim and objective it must be governed and administered by a principal or

headmaster. This means that no school can function effectively without effective administration. School administration includes the management of school operations from creating a safe learning environment to managing the school budget.

Therefore, effective administrative activities include: the administration of personnel programme, facilities and space management, purchase and maintenance of supplies and materials, communication and transportation services, health and safety. The principles of institutional administrative structure are pertinent to governance, organizational effectiveness and financial/physical management of the institutions. It is expected that each office/unit will establish goals, which derive from and support the purpose of the institution. For a school to function effectively it must evaluate the process in achieving these goals, and use the evaluation in making appropriate modifications in resources, programmes and management. To achieve effective performance in any institution, according to Blunt and Collins (2014), the school is expected to provide for: planning and executive direction, administrative and logistical services, services and conveniences for the institution's employees, enhancing relationships with institution constituencies and recruiting and admitting students to the institution's educational programmes

Hence the administrative structures of Secondary Schools settings must therefore have a direct influence on the classroom instructional processes and performance of students. According to Adebayo (2021), there has to be administration in any organization as long as an organization consists of people brought together in hierarchical set-ups, making use of tools, equipment, human and material resources, all in the quest of attaining the goals for which the organization is established and in this case

the school is established for the sole purpose of improving the life of the students who in turn better the society. The administration of a school has the responsibility for bringing together its various resources and allocating them effectively to accomplish goals. Although, the organizational pattern of an institution is important to the institution's development and affects the morale of all its members.

School administrative structure has a direct bearing on state educational policies. It should be stated here also, that effective use of instructional materials by teachers for proper motivation of students is as a result of orderly supervision and administration. Most resourceful teachers are made to be resourceful through supervision undertaken within the school by supervisors. Varied scholars of psychology and other professionals in education have posited that, students learn when instructional materials are provided; that the teacher motivates his students in a particular lesson if instructional materials are available. Alternatively, in the absence of school-provided instructional materials, the teacher is advised to carry his students along in the classroom setting. In most cases, a supervisor would question the teachers where teaching or instruction does not include instructional materials to support or explain the subject matter categorically. Thus, administrative structure and supervision have positively enhanced school instructional processes and learning thus increasing and improving students' performance, Rivers State UBE Board (2017).

As educating a nation remains vital strategy for the development of the society throughout the developing world, studies on human capital development concur that it is the human resources of a nation and not its capital or natural resources that ultimately determine the pace of its economic and

social development. The principal institutional mechanism for developing human capital is the formal education system of primary, secondary, and tertiary training (Nsubuga, 2013). Muthondu (2017) opined that the world is changing very rapidly and indeed this speed of change makes it almost impossible for any person of either gender or preferred administrative style to have all the knowledge, insight or power to achieve success. The old form of administration that gave power and a title to one or few individuals, in most cases the males is rapidly becoming dysfunctional and jettison. Potential leaders of any gender should train themselves to adapt to the changing society and make every effort to teach and model the style of administration which will most effectively lead the institution into achieving its set goals.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to identify the impact of school administrative structure on the academic performance of secondary school students. Specifically the study ought to:-

1. Determine the extent to which a good organized hierarchy of authority impact on the academic performance of secondary school students in Enugu Education zone in Enugu State.
2. Determine the extent to which efficient and effective communication impact on the academic performance of secondary school students in Enugu Education zone in Enugu State.
3. Determine the extent to which division of labour through delegation of authority impact on secondary school students' academic performance of male and female in Enugu Education zone in Enugu State.

Research Questions

1. To what extent does a good organized hierarchy of authority impact on academic

performance of secondary school students in Enugu educational zone in Enugu state?

2. To what Extent does efficient and effective communication impact on the academic performance of secondary school students in Enugu educational zone in Enugu state?

3. To what Extent does division of labour through delegation of authority impact on the academic performance of secondary school students in Enugu educational zone in Enugu state?

Hypotheses of the Study

H0₁: There is no significant difference between the opinions of principals on one hand, and teachers on the other hand, with regard to the impact of good hierarchy of authority on the school administrative structure on the academic performance of secondary school students' academic performance in Enugu Education zone in Enugu state.

H0₂: There is no significant difference between the opinions of principals on one hand, and teachers on the other hand, with regard to impact of efficient and effective communication on the school administrative structure on academic performance of secondary school students in Enugu Education zone in Enugu state.

H0₃: There is no significant difference between the opinions of principals on one hand, and teachers on the other hand, with regard to the impact of division of labour on the school administrative structure on academic performance of secondary school students in Enugu Education zone in Enugu state.

Conceptual Framework

School Administrative System

It is important to conceptualize school administration as a social process. A social system involves two classes of phenomena which are independent and interactive. The first class consists of the institution, its roles and expectations which are in line with the goals of the system.

Hornby (2017) defined state schools as ‘public school, a school that is paid for by the government. In the National policy on education (2018) the purpose of secondary education shall be to prepare the students for useful living within the society and to prepare the student for higher education. One of the goals of secondary education is to offer diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, opportunities and future roles. Public schools are those secondary schools funded by the state government. Government recruits their own teachers who take care of the students and the facilities in the school compound. The federal or state government takes full control of those secondary schools by providing all the necessary infrastructures for effective teaching and learning.

The Secondary Grammar Schools are patterned on the English grammar school with its’ classical traditions. Comprehensive Secondary Schools in Nigeria are run on the comprehensive system. In these schools the first two or three years are spent on general education in which wide range of academic, practical and vocational subjects such as English Language, History, Geography, Religious Studies, Social studies, Sciences (physics, Chemistry, Biology) Agriculture, Mathematics, technical drawing, Welding Arts, Crafts and Home Economics. The main aim of giving general education during the first two or three years is to allow the students to find out, where their natural interests lie either for purely secondary grammar school type of subjects or for purely technical subjects. It is expressed that comprehensive secondary schools are usually expensive to build and to equip. Many more collages are being modified to be comprehensive in nature. Technical Trade Schools provide pre-vocational training courses for primary school leavers. The institution offers courses in technical subjects such as woodwork, metalwork,

technical drawing, building, welding, motor mechanics etc.

In this work, public secondary school being considered is comprehensive in nature. Secondary education as stated in National Policy on Education is divided into two stages: 3-years junior secondary and 3-years senior secondary. Curricula of the junior secondary school include Mathematics, English, Language, Integrated Science, Social Studies, Practical Agriculture amongst others. At the end of the three years Junior Certificate Examination successful candidates proceed to Senior Secondary Schools, technical Collages and Teachers’ Collages depending on the ability of the child. Curricula activities of the Senior Secondary Schools include Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Geography, Mathematics, English History and Agricultural Science or Vocational Subjects. At the three years, evaluation of the study is done through writing West African School Certificate Exams and recently NECO and NABTEB. To get admission into higher institution, the student must have credit in 5 subjects, including English and Mathematics.

According to Eze (2018), Public schools are those schools which are owned, managed, controlled, financed and supervised by the federal/state government through the state ministry of education and post primary school management board. In public school government give continuous financial support as well as supervision and inspection. These public schools could be a Single sex type; Co-educational and boarding school either for boys or girls.

Administrative Structure

Structure in an organization are positions that determine goals of an organization, it indicates role expectations as well as distribution of formal authority among various positions. it implies the framework within which people act. Stieglitz

(2019) defined institutional (school) structure as the process of logically grouping activities, delineating authority and responsibility, and establishing work relationship that will enable both the organization and individuals to realize their mutual objectives. Edgar and James (2021) described institutional design and structure as a powerful way to change and influence people’s behaviour. It shows the chain of command and the type of relationship that exists between two individuals – the super-ordinates and the subordinates.

According to Obilade (2017) two major kinds of Administrative Structure are common to all institutions these structures are **Flat** and **Tall Administrative Structure in Secondary School**

Secondary School Organogram: A graphical representation of the administrative structure.

Structures. It is noteworthy that the type of span of control adopted will influence the shape of the organizational structure. A wide span of control means that the administrator supervises a large number of people or has a large number of people reporting to him. This situation is referred to as flat structure. A narrow span of control requires that the institution has more levels in the hierarchy and the structure looks very much like a pyramid; this is known as tall structure. By implication therefore, a tall administrative structure is characterized by many hierarchy levels between the lowest and the highest positions in the hierarchy.

Source: Girls Secondary School Abakpa, Enugu. (2021)

The following characteristics are typical of organizational structures, organogram or charts:

- Each box represents a position occupied by an individual in the organization;
- The higher the position the higher the authority associated with it;
- Each lower position is accountable to the position above it; and
- There is a relationship between the position, individuals and roles in the organization.

Okoroma (2017)

The impact of efficient and effective communication on academic performance of secondary school students

This is a process that involves the transmission and accurate replication of ideas with ensured feedback, which elicit actions necessary for goals accomplishment. All administrators require effective communication to facilitate their interpersonal, informational and decisional roles. Neil Kokemuller (2017) opined that basically **communication effectiveness** means you deliver a message the receiver understands it exactly as you intended, though perfect communication is rare, given the filters that can get in the way of effective delivery or receipt of the message while **communication efficiency** is that you deliver your message quickly in a way that allows the receiver to hear it, interpret and make use of it as you intended. Effective communication also helps educational administrators to fulfill their executive functions of planning, organizing, motivating, resolving conflicts and controlling activities all of which are linked to accountability. Effective communication also promotes a spirit of understanding, mutual trust, confidence and co-operation amongst the individuals within and outside a school system. This

can enhance job satisfaction and create in employees a high sense of belonging and loyalty to the organization. This, no doubt, can be an effective parameter for future accountability Omoregie (2021).

According to Bidmos (2018) Good information is that which is encoded by the sender and decoded by the user the way and manner intended by the sender. For information to be good, the following characteristics must be present, Relevance; Information must be relevant to the problem in question. It is a well-known fact that reports, messages, tabulations etc contain irrelevant parts which most often prevent the user of the information to get the actual meaning of what the sender wants. Accuracy: Although absolute accuracy of information cannot be achieved, information should be sufficiently accurate for management reliance and for the purpose for which it is meant.

The Impact of Division of Labour through Delegation of Authority

Since it is not possible for a head of an institution to perform all tasks and functions alone, there is need, therefore, to divide or break the work down into a number of tasks, such that others are charged with the responsibilities of carrying out those tasks Okoroma (2017). This principle leads to specialization and engenders high efficiency and productivity. According to Chrudenand Sherman (2016) and EDA (2018), division of labour or work is the breaking down of work into smaller units in which experts are assigned to the departments where they can most function to increase productivity and greater efficiency. This is also to encourage specialization; authority and responsibility so as to enable him perform as expected of him. That is why we have levels of position with attached responsibility and authority for instance the principal, dean of studies, heads of department,

sectional heads, head teachers, form teachers, subject teachers and nonacademic staff of the school all working together hand in hand to ensure the graduation of literate students.

In the context of management, authority is the right to take action in directing and coordinating the activities of others for the purpose of achieving the goals of an organization. It also involves the right to use discretion in handling activities. Authority is normally the position an individual is occupying and not in the individual as a person. It provides the force that binds the various units or departments of an organization together. Through the process of delegation, authority is passed downward within the organization and divided among subordinate personnel. Responsibility has been defined as “an obligation of an individual to perform the functions assigned to him to the best of his ability and in accordance with stated directives” (Okoroma, 2017). This definition is made clear by the following point. Employees within an organization have responsibilities that are determined by the duties of their respective jobs and by the assignments given to them by their superior officers. When jobs (duties) are assigned to subordinates by their superiors the subordinates have obligations to perform such duties. It is this obligation that is called responsibility (Chruden and Sherman, 2020). The responsibility of managing an organization is usually assigned to a chief executive who may be a managing director, principal, provost, vice-chancellor or commissioner.

Theoretical Framework

Classical Management Theory

Classical Approach to School Administration, this school of thought championed by Taylor (2015) described administration as a systematic process of carrying out a definite task which includes planning, organizing, staffing, directing, coordinating, reporting and budgeting.

Having had accumulated experiences as industrial employee, Taylor noted that people could be made to work efficiently as machine by employing scientific methods as opposed to intuitive approach. Though in this new method, he argued that wastages and inefficiency would be avoided. The key to the scientific approach is the “concept of man as machinery”. With this, he proposed that financial reward (motivation) is a major factor that can make workers work more efficiently.

Empirical Review

Suleiman, et al (2016) carried out a study to determine the relationship between principals’ administrative styles and students’ academic performance in Taraba State secondary schools, Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to determine the relationships between initiative structure of leadership styles, consideration of structure of leadership styles, participatory structure of leadership styles as they affect students’ academic performance. The results of the study revealed that there were no significant relationships between principals initiative administrative styles and students’ academic performance in English language. The findings also revealed no significant relationships between consideration structure of principals’ administrative styles and students’ academic performance in English language. The findings further revealed no significant relationships between participatory administrative styles of principals’ and student academic performance in senior secondary schools in English language for the year 2015, and in Mathematics 2010 and 2011 respectively. It further revealed that among the three leadership styles, none is the best predictor of students’ academic performance in Taraba State secondary schools. Based on these findings, it was

recommended among others that School administrators should explore ways and means of using varying administrative styles that could yield the much needed results of enhancing students' academic performance.

Methods

The population of the study was 996 teachers and Principals in Enugu Educational Zone of Enugu State made up of 920 teachers and 76 principals in the zone. Stratified Random sampling technique was adopted in the study that resulted to 122 sample size used in the study.

The research questions were analyzed descriptively using mean and standard deviation based on a 4 – point Likert Scale of Very Great Extent (VGE) 4pts, Great Extent (GE) 3pts, Little Extent (LE) 2pts and Very Little Extent (VLE) 1 pt. In the case of analysis of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance, Z – test was used, when Z value (calculated) was less than critical value (of 1.96), the null hypothesis was accepted as significant but when the (critical Z - value) is greater than table value, the null hypothesis of no significance was rejected.

Results

(Research Question One)

Table 1

Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation of Principals and Teachers on the Extent to which good organized hierarchy of authority impact on academic performance of secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone.

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Principals			Teachers		
		-- X	SD	Decision	-- X	SD	Decisi on
1	Flow of authority from highest echelon down to the lowest echelon	2.78	0.78	A	3.15	0.96	A
2	Delegation of positions of authority	2.55	0.61	A	3.13	0.91	A
3	Direct report of subordinates to immediate superiors	2.71	0.58	A	3.13	0.93	A
4	Supervision of the activities of tutorial and non tutorial staff	3.07	0.66	A	2.82	0.88	A
5	Monitoring of teachers progress high echelon down to the low echelon	3.09	0.77	A	2.78	0.83	A
	Grand Mean	2.84	0.68	A	3.00	0.92	A

Key: S/N = Serial Number, X = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, A = Accepted, R = Rejected Hypothesis one

Table 2 Z-Test Analysis of Mean Response scores of Principals and Teachers on the impact of good organized hierarchy of authority on the school administrative structure on students’ academic performance in secondary schools are presented on the table below.

Key: N = Number of Respondents, X = Mean , SD = Standard Deviation

Variables	N	-- X	SD	DF	Level of significant	Z-Cal	Z-tab
Extent to which Good hierarchy of authority impact on students’ academic performance							
Principals	76	2.84	0.68	120	0.05	-6.53	1.96
Teachers	46	3.00	0.92				

D f = Degree of Freedom Z Cal = Z-Calculated, Z- tab = Z table

The calculated Z-Value, value at 120 degree and 0.05 level of significance is -6.53. Since the calculated value of -6.53 is less than the critical table value of 1.96, the null hypotheses is accepted. This is to say that, there was no significant difference

between the opinion of the Principals and Teachers on the extent to which good hierarchy of authority impact on academic performance of secondary school students’ in Enugu educational zone in Enugu State.

Research Question Two:

Table 3 Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation of Principals and Teachers on the extent effective and efficient communication impact on academic performance of secondary school students in Enugu Educational Zone in Enugu State are presented on the table below after computation.

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Principals			Teachers		
		-- X	SD	Decision	-- X	SD	Decision
6	Free Flow of Information from Principal to Teachers	3.01	1.01	A	2.65	0.72	A
7	Timely Release of Information	2.69	1.12	A	3.17	0.80	A
8	Preparation and adequate delivery of lessons	2.72	0.70	A	3.13	0.83	A
9	Adequate Teacher- Student interaction	2.73	0.81	A	2.84	0.87	A
10	Adequate Feedback learner	2.78	0.99	A	3.02	0.86	A

Mechanism							
Grand mean	2.78	0.94	A	2.96	0.81	A	

Key: S/N = Serial Number, X = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, A= Accepted,R = Rejected

Hypotheses Two:

Table 4 Z- Test Analysis shows the Mean Response scores of Principals and Teachers on the impact of effective and efficient communication of the school administrative structure on students’ academic performance in Enugu Education Zone Enugu State.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	Level of significant	Z -Cal	Z -tab
Extent to which effective and efficient communication of authority impact on students academic performance in secondary schools							
Principals	76	2.78	0.94	120	0.05	- 6.95	1.96
Teachers	46	2.96	0.81				

Key: N = Number of Respondents, X = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, Df = Degree of Freedom

Z Cal = Z- Calculated, Z- tab = Z table

The calculated Z- value of 120 degree and 0.05 level of significance is -6.95. Since the calculated value of -6.95 is less than the critical table value of 1.96, the null hypotheses is accepted. This is to say that, there

was no significant difference between the opinion of the Principals and Teachers on the extent to which effective and efficient communication impact on students’ academic performance in secondary schools in Enugu educational zone in Enugu State.

Research Question Three:

Table 5 Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation of Principals and Teachers on the extent to which division of labour through delegation of authority impact on academic performance of secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone in Enugu State.

S/N	Questionnaire items	Principals			Teachers		
		-- X	SD	Decision	-- X	SD	Decision
11	Job description	3.13	0.96	A	3.19	0.58	A
12	Departmentalization	3.35	0.77	A	2.78	0.77	A
13	Delegation of authority	3.28	0.83	A	2.86	0.79	A
14	Specification of Individual staff schedule of duties	3.02	0.96	A	2.80	0.81	A
15	Coordination and control of all activities	2.89	0.91	A	2.91	0.88	A
	Grand mean	3.13	0.88	A	2.90	0.76	A

Hypotheses Three:

Table 6 Z- Test Analysis shows the Mean Response scores of Principals and Teachers on the extent to which division of labour impact on students’ academic performance in secondary schools in Enugu Educational Zone Enugu State.

Variables	N	-- X	SD	DF	Level of Significant	Z -Cal	Z -tab
Extent to which to which division of labour impact on students academic performance in secondary schools students in Enugu educational zone							

Principals	76	3.13	0.88	120	0.05	-20.25	1.96
Teachers	46	2.90	0.76				

The calculated Z- value of 120 degree and 0.05 level of significance is -20.25. Since the calculated value of -20.25 is less than the critical table value of 1.96, the null hypotheses is accepted. This is to say that, there was no significant difference between the opinion of the Principals and Teachers on the extent to which division of labour impact on academic performance secondary school students’ in Enugu educational zone in Enugu State.

Discussions of Findings

From Table 1, the test shows that the two respondents were in agreement that all the items impact on academic performance of secondary school students in Enugu educational zone. This is in agreement with Muli (2015), Muthondu (2017) and NERDC (2018) who noted that twenty five percent of the total factors causing failure or success of students are decided by the nature of school leadership and administrative qualities. It is also in line with NOUN (2019) assertion that a good administrative structure can only impact positively on student’s academic performance if the school has a clearly defined functions for the staff as well as the degree of authority to be exercised by the functionaries in their offices. This means that organizational efficiency can only be pronounced when members know what they are expected of them to do and to whom they are responsible to if backed up with a commensurate authority either from top down to the lowest echelon or from lowest echelon to the top in the hierarchy order.

In Table 3, all the questionnaire items agreed that effective and efficient communication, impact positively on academic performance of secondary

school students. This is in line with the views expressed by Omoregie(2021) that effective communication is the only parameter for future accountability in teaching and learning. This result is also in line with Neil (2017) who opined that basically communication effectiveness can only be accepted if the message delivered is understood by the receiver exactly the way you intended it to be even though perfect communication is rare, given the filters that can get in the way of effective delivery or receipt of the message while communication efficiency is that you deliver your message quickly in a way that allows the receiver to hear it, interpret and make use of it as you intended.

Table 5 shows that non specification of duties, job description, departmentalization of duties, roles, and functions, delegation of authorities, coordination and control of workers or staff activities in form of division of labour can impact negatively on students’ academic performance in secondary schools. This is in line with the views expressed by Sherman et al (2018), that since it is not possible for the head of an institution to perform all tasks and functions alone, that there is need therefore to divide or break the work done into a number of tasks, such that others are charged with the responsibility of carrying out those tasks. The idea according to them is to assign experts to the departments where they can most function in order to increase productivity, greater efficiency, encourage specialization; authority and responsibility so as to enable people perform as expected of them. and good management to achieve

good academic performance of students in external and internal environments.

Summary of Findings

i. Research question one is on the extent to which good organized hierarchy of authority impact on academic performance of secondary school students in Enugu educational zone in Enugu state. The results show that flow of authority, delegation of positions of authority, direct report of subordinates to immediate superior, supervision of the activities of tutorial and non-tutorial staff and monitoring of teacher's progress from high echelon down to the low echelon have positive impacts on students' academic performance in secondary schools.

ii. Research question two is on the extent to which efficient and effective communication impact on academic performance of secondary school students in Enugu educational zone. The study reveals that free flow of information from the principal to the teachers, timely release of information, preparation and adequate delivery of lessons, adequate teacher-student interaction and adequate learner feedback mechanism have positive impacts on secondary schools academic performance if well-articulated to enhance teaching and learning.

iii. Research question three is on the extent to which division of labor impact on academic performance of secondary school students in Enugu educational zone reveals that job description, departmentalization, delegation and specifications of individual staff's schedules of duty and coordination and control of all activities will impact positively on students' academic performance in secondary schools if the school administrative structure is effectively utilized.

Conclusions

The following conclusions have been drawn from major findings of the study. This study has agreed to

“ a great extent” and “a very great extent” that having a good organized hierarchy of authority, efficient and effective communication, division of labor, adequate provision of physical facilities and equipment, availability of fund for implementation of organizational programs and availability of adequate personnel will impact positively on secondary school students academic performance in Enugu educational zone, if these school administrative structures are enhanced for teaching and learning. This is to say that availability of quantitative and qualitative educational facilities in secondary schools will possibly impact on student academic performance in schools. This means that administrative structures put in place in the school environment to a great extent will determine how much learning and teaching will be possible in a school system

Recommendations

Based on the finding of the study and the educational implications of the study, the researcher recommends that:

i. Secondary schools in Enugu educational zone in Enugu State must have a good hierarchy of authority where information can flow freely from top to down to the lowest hierarchy without any hindrances on the way to prevent haphazard and lopsided information and planning which may lead to uncertainty, risks and waste of scarce resources. .

ii. Efficient and effective means of communication should be diverse so that there will be smooth communication between the State School Management Commission and those implementing education policies and objectives like teachers, principals, inspectors, supervisors, curriculum planners and administrators of educational services. This is to avoid communication bog down which if not taken care off immediately may affect students' academic performance in schools.

iii. Division of labour in form of delegation of authority to the subordinates should be vigorously pursued if students' academic performance in secondary schools is to be achieved. To this end, the role expectation of teachers, students, principals, heads of department, sectional heads and other groups in secondary school system, should be specified, departmentalized, described and well-coordinated to enhance students' academic performance in schools.

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- vi. Finally adequate personnel should be recruited to teach students in the secondary schools. This is to avoid shortage of manpower in the educational sector which if left unattended to, may affect students' academic performance in schools. Regular training and retraining of teachers or sponsorship of staff for seminars, workshops and conferences will go a long way to enhance students' academic performance. Such training will also help develop them professionally in terms of knowledge and skills in chosen subject area of specialization
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